

Review Paper

Some Medicinal Plants used for Depression

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Abstract:- Medicinal plants and their extracts are natural remedies with enormous potential for treating various diseases including depression. In the case of depression hundreds of plants have traditionally been used in folk medicine for generations. Moreover some specific plants are excellent for this purpose because of their appearance small and medicinal properties. Research too supports the idea that growing plants at home can have a positive impact on individuals diagnosed with depression. Depression is a very painful and painful experience because it destroys the will to live of a person suffering from depression we should do everything possible to deal with this type of mental illness and plants are one of it.

Keywords:- Depression, Medicinal Plants, Remedies, Illness, Properties, Research, Suffering, Painful.

I. INTRODUCTION

Depression is a common mental disorder. Depression is a mental illness or mental disorder in which a person feels lonely, hopeless, sad, low self-esteem, symptom such as loss of appetite and excessive sleepiness in a person suffering from depression. Depression is like dissolving a poison in our life which is a biological process done by our body for many types of problems in our daily life which we call stress which is normal for a short time or found in everyone but if it is found in person for a long time so it can cause trouble if it is included in our habit then it proves fatal for us. Depression can last for several weeks, months or years for many people with depression symptoms usually are severe enough to cause noticeable problems in day-to-day activities. Such as work, school, social activities or relationships with others, some people may feel generally miserable or unhappy without really knowing why. Some plants have been studied for their potential antidepressant activity. Lavender, jade plant, Aloe vera, Lemon Balm, Hypericum performance (St. John's wort) is a well-known herbal medicinal treatment.

II. METHOD AND MATERIAL

❖ Best Indoor Plants for Depression

Indoor plants not only purify the air but they also provide us with mental happiness. In today's hectic life, negativity can come in our daily life and we can curb it by plants. Scientific research has proven that growing indoor plants for depression is a great option to have a positive impact on your mental health.

- Lemon Balm – Botanical Name – *Melissa officinalis*.
- Jasmine - Botanical Name – *Jasminum*
- Lavender-Botanical Name – *Lavandula*
- Flamingo Lily-Botanical Name – *Anthurium andraeanum*.
- Chamomile – Botanical Name – *Matricaria Chamomilla*
- Peace Lily - Botanical Name – *Spathiphyllum*
- Aloe vera Botanical Name- *Aloe barbadensis miller*
- 8. Jade Plant-Botanical Name- *Crassula ovate*
- 9. Snake Plant-Botanical Name- *Sansevieria trifasciata*
- 10. Pothos - Botanical Name – *Epipremnum aureum*

➤ *Jasmine – (Genus Jasmine)*

Also spelled Jessamine, genus of about 200 species of fragrant flowered shrubs and vines of the olive family (oleaceae). Most true Jasmines have climbing branches without tendrils. The white, yellow or rarely pink flowers. Jasmine's scent directly impacts a brain nervous system chemical known as GABA. Which results in the calming of the nerves, a soothing of depression.

➤ *Lavender (Lavender angustifolia)*

Is an evergreen plant native to the Mediterranean. Its flower and oil have a popular scent and are also used as medicine. Lavender oil activated OXT neurons in the PVN of the hypothalamus which contributed to its antidepressant effects. These results suggest that aromatherapy using lavender essential oils might improve depressive mood in healthy individuals. Lavender has a long history of medicinal use and is suggested to pass as anticonvulsant antidepressive.

➤ *Aloe Vera*

Aloe Vera is a succulent plant species of the genus *aloe*, an evergreen perennial that originates from the Arabian peninsula but grows wild in tropical, semi-tropical and arid climates around the world.

➤ *Jade Plant*

Crassula ovata commonly known as jade plant, lucky plant, money plant or money tree is a succulent plant with small pink or white flowers. Jade plant has gained popularity as a house plant due to easy maintenance and medicinal benefits. Jade plants can cleanse the air from pollutants that spread through paint and cleaning products, which include chemicals that can make you feel stressed and unwell.

➤ *Snake Plants*

Dracaena trifasciata is a species of flowering plant in the family Asparagaceae native to tropical west Africa from Nigeria east to the Congo it is most commonly known as the snake plant. Snake plant can help improve indoor air by absorbing air borne toxic pollutants that impact your sleep mood and energy levels.

➤ *Peace lily*

Spathiphyllum is a genus of about 47 species of monocotyledonous flowering plants in the family Araceae. Native to tropical regions of the Americas and southeastern Asia The peace lily is the most popular low maintenance houseplant with showy prominent white bracts and shiny green foliage It also harmful toxins and VOCs from the air which has a positive impact on your mood and health.

III. RESULT

A Total of 10 plants species are related to Antidepressant properties all over views the medicinal plant play an important role in depression over all the whole plant species enumerating the Botanical name and local name.

IV. DISCUSSION

Plants are more easily recognized by their local names and medicinal properties in every part of the world in the increasing population today people are becoming more victims of depression apart from this. As we all know that after the corona virus pandemic a fear has settled in the minds of people and many people also became victims of depression during this period plants play an important role in relieving depression many people are turning to herbal remedies to treat depression plants are important in the traditional treatment of various diseases including depression. Are st. John Lavender Jasmine A Lemn Balm Jade plant Bamboo sage weeping described these more detail.

V. CONCLUSION

Here we described over ten of the best plants for depression Before we began we explained how plants can help with a mental health disorder like depression The best plants to help you with depression are St. John's wort, Lavender, Jasmine Aloe vera, Lemn Balm, Jade plant, Holy Basil Lucky Bamboo, sage, weeping Fig. Pothos we described these plants in more detail.

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REFERENCES

- [1]. Rahmati B, Kiasalari Z, Roghani M, Khalili M, Ansari F. Antidepressant and anxiolytic activity of *Lavandula officinalis* aerial parts hydroalcoholic extract in scopolamine- treated rats. *Pharm Biol* 2017; 55(1): 958-65.
- [2]. Maria de Souza JM, Lira Ferrari GS, Bucalen Ferrari CK. Correlates of geriatric depression scale with perceived quality of life in an elderly population. *Geriatr Persia* 2018;2: e01.
- [3]. Rajput MS, Sinha S, Mathur V, Agrawal P. Herbal antidepressants. *IJPFR* 2011; 1(1):159-69.
- [4]. Dwyer AV, Whitten DL, Hawrelak JA. Herbal medicines, other than St. John's Wort, in the treatment of depression. *Sci Rev Altern Med* 2011; 1;16(1): 281-4.
- [5]. Tegegne MT, Mossie TB, Awoke AA, Assaye AM, Gebrie BT, Eshetu DA. Depression and anxiety disorder among epileptic people at Amanuel Specialized Mental Hospital, AddisAbaba, Ethiopia. *BMC Psychiatry* 2015; 15(1): 210.
- [6]. Rabiei Z, Rabie S. A review on antidepressant effect of medicinal plants. *Bangladesh J Pharmacol* 2017; 12(1): 1-11.
- [7]. Moragrega I, Ríos JL. Medicinal plants in the treatment of depression: evidence from preclinical studies. *Planta Med* 2021. doi:10.1055/a-1338-1011
- [8]. Miller AH, Raison CL. The role of inflammation in depression: from evolutionary imperative to modern treatment target. *Nat Rev Immunol* 2016;16: 22–34
- [9]. Jha MK, Trivedi MH. Personalized antidepressant selection and pathway to novel treatments: clinical utility of targeting inflammation. *Int J Mol Sci* 2018; 19: 233
- [10]. Setiawan E, Attwells S, Wilson AA, Mizrahi R, Rusjan PM, Miler L, Xu C, Sharma S, Kish S, Houle S, Meyer JH. Association of translocator protein total distribution volume with duration of untreated major depressive disorder: a cross-sectional study. *Lancet Psychiatry* 2018; 5: 339–347
- [11]. Zunszain PA, Hepgul N, Pariante CM. Inflammation and depression. *Curr Topics Behav Neurosci* 2013; 14: 135–151
- [12]. Christmas DM, Potokar J, Davies SJ. A biological pathway linking inflammation and depression: activation of indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase. *Neuropsychiatr Dis Treat* 2011; 7: 431–439
- [13]. Pariante CM. Why are depressed patients inflamed? A reflection on 20 years of research on depression, glucocorticoid resistance and inflammation. *Eur Neuropsychopharmacol* 2017; 27: 554–559
- [14]. Frodl TS, Koutsouleris N, Bottlender R, Born C, Jäger M, Scupin I, Reiser M, Möller HJ, Meisenzahl EM. Depression-related variation in brain morphology over 3 years: effects of stress? *Arch Gen Psychiatry* 2008; 65:1156–1165

- [15]. Yu JJ, Pei LB, Zhang Y, Wen ZY, Yang JL. Chronic supplementation of curcumin enhances the efficacy of antidepressants in major depressive disorder: a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled pilot study. *J Clin Psychopharmacol* 2015; 35: 406–410
- [16]. Sahebkar A, Cicero AFG, Simental-Mendía LE, Aggarwal BB, Gupta SC. Curcumin downregulates human tumor necrosis factor- α levels: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Pharmacol Res* 2016; 107: 234–242
- [17]. Sarris J. Herbal medicines in the treatment of psychiatric disorders: 10-year updated review. *Phytother Res* 2018; 32: 1147–1162
- [18]. Maes M, Yirmiya R, Norberg J, Brene S, Hibbeln J, Perini G, Kubera M, Bob P, Lerer B, Maj M. The inflammatory and neurodegenerative (I&ND) hypothesis of depression: leads for future research and new drug developments in depression. *Metab Brain Dis* 2009; 24: 27–53
- [19]. Raison CL, Miller AH. Is depression an inflammatory disorder? *Curr Psychiatry Rep* 2011; 13: 467–475
- [20]. Leonard B, Maes M. Mechanistic explanations how cell-mediated immune activation, inflammation and oxidative and nitrosative stress pathways and their sequels and concomitants play a role in the pathophysiology of unipolar depression. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev* 2012; 36: 764–785
- [21]. Lopresti AL, Hood SD, Drummond PD. Multiple antidepressant potential modes of action of curcumin: a review of its anti-inflammatory, monoaminergic, antioxidant, immune-modulating and neuroprotective effects. *J Psychopharmacol* 2012; 26: 1512–1524
- [22]. Vадnie CA, McClung CA. Circadian rhythm disturbances in mood disorders: insights into the role of the suprachiasmatic nucleus. *Neural Plast* 2017; 2017: 1504507
- [23]. Miller AH, Raison CL. Immune system contributions to the pathophysiology of depression. *Focus* 2008; 6: 36–45